

The Relation between the Surface Tension and Vapour Pressure of Binary Mixtures.

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It is a well known fact that the curve, representing the relation between vapour pressure and composition usually belongs to one of three main types:—

(a) The vapour pressures of the mixture may lie between those of the pure components.

(b) The vapour pressure curve may have a maximum.

(c) The vapour pressure curve may have a minimum.

It was expected that the surface tension of binary mixtures would also give similar types of curves and in order to determine the exact relationship between surface tensions and vapour pressures, the present investigation was undertaken.

Moreover attempts have been made by Volkmann and Whatmough and others to obtain suitable formulæ for calculating the surface tensions of mixtures. Volkmann (*Ann. Physik*, 188, [iii], 320) suggested that the surface tension of binary mixtures can be represented by the formula—

$$\gamma = \gamma_1 v_1 + \gamma_2 v_2$$

where γ represents the surface tension of the mixture, γ_1 and γ_2 represent the surface tension of the components, v_1 and v_2 volumes of the liquids taken fractionally. This formula has got many exceptions. Later on Whatmough (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1902, 39, 158) modified the above formula and took into account the volume changes which

take place on mixing and proposed the following formula :—

$$\gamma = R(\gamma_1 v_1 + \gamma_2 v_2)$$

where γ , γ_1 , γ_2 , v_1 , v_2 have the same significance as before and R is the ratio of the calculated to the observed density. By the help of the data obtained as the result of the present investigation, the validity of the above-mentioned formulæ was tested by comparing the observed values with the values calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Zawidski (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, 35, 129) has determined the vapour pressure of a large number of binary mixtures and from his work the following mixtures, belonging to each of the three characteristic types, were selected for the present investigation.

1. Mixtures, the vapour pressure curves of which correspond with a straight line.

- (a) Benzene and ethylene dichloride.
- (b) Ethylene dibromide and propylene dibromide.
- (c) Bromobenzene and toluene.
- (d) Chlorobenzene and toluene.

2. Mixtures, the vapour pressure curves of which pass through a minimum.

- (a) Acetic acid and pyridine.
- (b) Chloroform and acetone.
- (c) Methyl alcohol and ethyl iodide.

3. Mixtures, the vapour pressure curves of which pass through a maximum.

- (a) Ethyl iodide and ethyl acetate.
- (b) Carbon tetrachloride and ethyl acetate.
- (c) Carbon disulphide and acetone.
- (d) Carbon tetrachloride and ethyl iodide.

Purification of the Chemicals.

The chemicals were all purified by the usual methods. In case of pyridine, however, the sample boiling between 112° – 116° was taken. Although this happens to be impure, yet reference to the work of Zawidski (*loc. cit.*) will show that the same sample was used by him in connection with his work on vapour pressure.

The method used for the determination of surface tension was the sphere detachment method due to Ferguson (*Phil. Mag.*, 26, 926).

Both Volkmann's and Whatmough's formulæ were used for obtaining values of surface tension by calculation but as Whatmough's formula was not found to show any decided advantage over Volkmann's formula, in the following tables calculated values in accordance with Volkmann's formula are only given.

1. *Benzene and Ethylene Dichloride.*

Vol. % Ethylene bromide.	γ at 17°		γ at 50°	
	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.
0	29.17	...	24.08	...
10	29.33	29.42	24.38	24.38
20	29.50	29.67	24.66	24.67
30	29.61	29.92	24.98	24.99
50	30.05	30.42	25.56	25.56
70	30.53	30.93	26.16	26.16
90	31.21	31.42	26.75	26.75
100	31.68		27.05	

2. *Propylene Dibromide and Ethylene Dibromide.*

Vol. % Propylene dibromide.	γ at 17°		γ at 40°		γ at 55°	
	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.
0	38.42	...	35.28	...	32.25	...
10	38.02	38.17	34.81	34.98	31.88	31.86
20	37.68	37.91	34.48	34.67	31.47	31.48
30	37.35	37.66	34.02	34.39	31.09	31.09
40	37.01	37.39	33.60	34.10	30.71	30.70
50	36.45	37.15	33.38	33.81	30.31	30.31
60	36.35	36.90	33.18	33.53	29.93	29.93
70	36.22	36.65	33.01	33.24	29.51	29.54
80	35.94	36.40	32.67	32.95	29.15	29.15
90	35.88	36.14	32.52	32.67	28.77	28.77
100	35.88	...	32.38	...	28.38	...

3. *Bromobenzene and Toluene.*

Vol. % Bromobenzene.	γ at 20°		γ at 35°		γ at 50°	
	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.
0	25.15	...	23.16	...	22.43	...
10	26.11	25.86	23.74	24.03	23.49	23.36
20	27.19	26.57	25.18	24.90	24.30	24.29
30	28.10	27.28	26.05	25.77	25.21	25.22
40	28.65	27.99	26.81	26.64	26.23	26.15
50	28.90	28.71	27.66	27.51	27.77	27.09
60	29.03	29.41	28.55	28.37	28.20	28.02
70	30.15	30.13	29.52	29.24	29.03	28.95
80	31.58	30.84	30.45	30.11	29.91	29.88
90	31.98	31.55	30.89	30.98	30.77	30.81
100	32.26	...	31.85	...	31.74	...

4. *Chlorobenzene and Toluene.*

Vol. % Chloro- benzene.	γ at 20°		γ at 35°		γ at 50°	
	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.
0	25·15	...	23·16	...	22·43	...
10	25·40	25·67	23·51	23·68	23·15	23·17
20	25·52	26·19	24·23	24·56	23·97	23·91
30	26·09	26·77	25·02	25·26	24·77	24·66
40	26·24	27·25	25·62	25·98	25·44	25·39
50	26·90	27·77	26·63	26·66	25·95	26·15
60	27·88	28·29	27·38	27·36	26·81	26·88
70	28·31	28·82	27·94	28·06	27·71	27·62
80	28·78	29·34	28·62	28·76	28·43	28·37
90	29·60	29·87	29·21	29·42	29·16	29·11
100	30·39	...	30·16	...	29·85	...

The observed and calculated values coincide very well in all these cases; hence we can say that when vapour pressures of mixtures obey the mixture law, the surface tensions of those mixtures also obey the mixture law, and when these values are plotted graphically, we get a straight line.

5. *Acetic Acid and Pyridine.*

Vol. % Acetic acid.	γ at 20°		γ at 40°		γ at 80°	
	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.
0	37.22	...	34.32	...	28.32	...
10	36.52	36.17	34.27	33.36	28.32	27.57
20	36.02	35.12	33.71	32.61	28.31	26.82
30	35.20	34.08	33.01	31.45	28.08	26.02
40	34.58	33.01	33.67	30.49	28.02	25.31
50	33.95	31.96	32.15	29.53	27.78	24.56
60	33.08	30.91	31.45	28.58	27.37	23.81
70	32.15	29.86	30.65	27.62	26.79	23.05
80	31.68	28.81	29.61	26.61	25.37	22.30
90	29.68	27.75	27.49	25.71	23.52	21.55
100	26.71	...	24.75	...	20.80	...

6. *Chloroform and Acetone.*

Vol. % Acetone.	γ at 15°		γ at 25°		γ at 35°	
	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.
0	27.29	...	25.67	...	24.92	...
10	27.05	26.92	25.56	25.34	24.81	24.54
20	26.78	26.56	25.43	25.01	24.65	24.16
30	26.48	26.19	25.25	24.68	24.48	23.80
40	26.18	25.85	25.06	24.35	24.18	23.40
50	25.88	25.45	24.81	23.92	23.92	23.02
60	25.45	25.09	24.58	23.69	23.61	22.67
70	25.15	24.72	24.24	23.36	23.29	22.26
80	24.66	24.35	23.75	23.03	22.83	21.88
90	24.17	23.99	23.18	22.69	22.07	21.50
100	23.62	...	22.37	...	21.18	...

7. *Methyl Alcohol and Ethyl Iodide.*

Vol. % Ethyl iodide.	γ at 25.2°		γ at 37.5°		γ at 45°	
	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.
0	19.65	...	18.97	...	18.46	...
10	20.75	20.72	20.04	19.93	19.49	19.29
20	23.66	21.79	22.90	20.89	21.81	20.13
30	25.12	22.87	23.81	21.86	22.95	20.97
40	26.04	23.95	24.62	22.82	23.60	21.80
50	26.80	25.02	24.88	23.78	24.23	22.64
60	27.03	26.09	26.02	24.75	24.81	23.74
70	28.21	27.17	26.78	25.71	25.34	24.31
80	28.98	28.24	27.46	26.67	25.82	25.14
90	29.61	29.32	28.18	27.64	26.37	25.97
100	30.39	...	28.60	...	26.81	...

In this case also we find that the observed values of surface tension are greater than those calculated while the vapour pressures are less than those calculated and the curve passes through maxima.

8. *Carbon Tetrachloride and Ethyl Acetate.*

Vol. % Ethyl acetate.	γ at 15°		γ at 35°		γ at 50°	
	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.
0	26.58	...	25.02	...	23.10	...
10	26.01	26.27	23.85	24.59	21.48	22.16
20	25.53	25.96	22.95	24.16	20.51	22.22
30	25.13	25.66	22.31	23.74	19.82	21.78
40	24.87	25.39	22.05	23.31	19.54	21.34
50	24.55	25.05	21.75	22.88	19.35	20.90
60	24.31	24.74	21.58	22.45	19.19	20.45
70	24.11	24.44	21.29	22.02	19.04	20.00
80	23.89	24.33	21.07	21.60	18.91	19.58
90	23.72	23.82	20.88	21.77	18.81	19.14
100	23.56	...	20.74	...	18.70	...

9. *Ethyl Acetate and Ethyl Iodide.*

Vol. % Ethyl acetate.	γ at 18°		γ at 35°		γ at 50°	
	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.
0	31.06	...	28.74	...	26.68	...
10	29.39	30.27	26.51	27.94	24.58	25.88
20	28.22	29.49	25.41	27.18	23.08	25.08
30	27.21	28.70	24.42	26.33	22.08	24.29
40	26.41	27.91	23.78	25.52	21.41	23.49
50	25.82	27.12	23.16	24.72	20.82	22.69
60	25.18	26.34	22.56	23.92	20.74	21.89
70	24.58	25.55	21.96	23.11	19.78	21.09
80	24.10	24.76	21.40	22.31	19.08	20.30
90	23.68	23.98	20.98	21.50	19.01	19.50
100	23.19	...	20.70	...	18.70	...

10. *Ethyl Iodide and Carbon Tetrachloride.*

Vol. % Ethyl iodide.	γ at 25.2°		γ at 37.5°		γ at 50°	
	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.
0	28.05	...	26.54	...	24.72	...
10	28.21	28.28	26.55	26.75	24.82	24.93
20	28.24	28.52	26.60	26.95	25.01	25.14
30	28.39	28.75	26.76	27.16	25.14	25.35
40	28.62	28.99	27.05	27.36	25.38	25.56
50	29.06	29.22	27.40	27.57	25.61	25.72
60	29.35	29.45	27.62	27.78	25.84	25.97
70	29.60	29.69	27.85	27.98	26.11	26.18
80	29.81	29.92	28.10	28.19	26.38	26.39
90	30.13	30.16	28.31	28.39	26.62	26.70
100	30.89	...	28.60	...	26.81	...

11. *Acetone and Carbon Disulphide.*

Vol. % Acetone.	γ at 15°		γ at 25°		γ at 35°	
	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.
0	23.06	...	21.62	...	21.17	...
10	23.64	24.09	22.28	22.69	21.89	22.19
20	24.69	25.13	23.20	23.76	23.16	23.21
30	24.88	26.17	24.38	24.84	23.38	24.23
40	25.58	27.20	24.74	25.91	24.12	25.25
50	26.58	28.24	25.20	26.98	25.02	26.27
60	27.33	29.27	26.03	27.99	25.82	27.29
70	28.32	30.31	27.02	29.12	26.86	28.32
80	29.64	31.24	28.36	30.19	28.07	29.34
90	31.70	32.38	29.93	31.27	29.17	30.36
100	33.41	...	32.24	...	31.38	...

Here we find that the observed values are much less than those calculated by Volkmann's formula and we sum up by saying that when the vapour pressure values of a mixture are greater than those calculated, the surface tension ones are less than those calculated, and thus when these values are plotted graphically, the curve will pass through minima.

Summary.

This investigation was undertaken with a view to find out a relation between surface tension and vapour pressure of binary mixtures and to see whether the mixtures, the vapour pressure curves of which show maxima, minima or straight lines, would behave similarly with respect to surface tension or not. Moreover it was tried to determine how far Volkmann's and Whatmough's formulæ were applicable for calculating the surface tension of mixtures. As a result of the present investigation the following results have been arrived at:—

1. When the vapour pressure curve is a straight line, the surface tension one is also a straight line.
2. When the vapour pressure curve shows a maximum, the surface tension one shows a minimum.
3. When the vapour pressure curve shows a minimum, the surface tension one shows a maximum.
4. Volkmann's formula was found applicable in case of those mixtures, the vapour pressure and surface tension of which are straight lines.
5. Whatmough's formula was not found to show any decided advantage over Volkmann's formula.